

TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING STUDENTS' MANAGEMENT ABILITIES BASED ON A SYNERGETIC EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the formation of students' management abilities based on a synergetic educational environment. Management ability is interpreted as a set of skills that includes independent planning, prioritization of tasks, organization of teamwork, decision-making, leadership, and reflective analysis. The study involved 84 third-year students. Questionnaires, pedagogical observation, the "Priority Setting" training, the Eisenhower Matrix, project-based learning, cooperative learning, and problem-based situations were used. The results showed that a synergetic educational environment is an effective pedagogical basis for developing students' management abilities.

In the modern higher education system, it is not enough for students to acquire only theoretical knowledge. They must also be able to make independent decisions, manage time, work in a team, plan tasks, and take responsibility for results. Therefore, the development of management abilities is one of the important tasks of higher education.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" defines improving the quality of education and ensuring the intellectual and professional development of the individual as one of the main priorities [1]. In addition, state policy aimed at improving the higher education system pays special attention to the integration of education, upbringing, research, and innovation [2]. This confirms the need to educate students as independent, initiative-driven, and management-ready individuals.

The synergetic approach serves as an important methodological basis for this process. It considers education as an open, interconnected, and self-organizing system. In such an environment, the student is not only a passive receiver of knowledge but also an active participant, organizer, and decision-maker in the educational process.

The theoretical foundations of the synergetic approach are connected with H. Haken's views on order and self-organization in complex systems [3]. In education, this approach explains how a new pedagogical result emerges through the interaction of various factors, such as the teacher, student, group, task, digital tool, and reflection.

L.S. Vygotsky interpreted education as a process of social cooperation and emphasized that student development is accelerated through communication and collaboration [4]. J.

Dewey considered experience-based learning as an important factor in developing personal activity and practical thinking [5]. These ideas show the importance of practical activity and teamwork in forming management abilities.

Project-based learning develops students' independent planning, task distribution, and result-oriented activity [6]. Cooperative learning forms collective responsibility, mutual support, and group management skills [7]. Problem-based learning develops students' analytical thinking, decision-making, and ability to apply knowledge in real-life situations [8].

Research Methodology

The study was conducted with the participation of 84 third-year students of Shahrizabz State Pedagogical Institute. The research methods included questionnaires, pedagogical observation, small-group work, the "Priority Setting" training, and classification of tasks based on the Eisenhower Matrix.

Students' management abilities were assessed according to the following criteria: independent planning, priority setting, coordination of teamwork, decision-making, leadership initiative, and reflective analysis. These criteria were combined with the main principles of the synergetic approach: openness, interconnection, flexibility, and self-organization.

Results. The survey results showed that 74 out of 84 students, or 88%, were satisfied with the communication and mentoring environment created by teachers. A total of 69 students, or 82%, stated that they needed methodological consultation on organizing research activities. In addition, 62 students, or 74%, indicated that they had practical professional skills.

During the "Priority Setting" training, students classified 20 tasks using the Eisenhower Matrix. As a result, 40 students correctly identified urgent tasks, 30 students identified important tasks, 12 students identified tasks that could be postponed, and 2 students identified low-priority tasks. The overall success rate was 84%.

The analysis of pedagogical methods showed that project-based learning developed independence by 92%, cooperative learning improved teamwork by 95%, and problem-based learning developed decision-making ability by 94%. These results confirm that different pedagogical methods develop different components of students' management abilities.

Table 1. Effectiveness of pedagogical methods in the development of management abilities (%)

Method	Independence	Teamwork	Decision-making	Leadership
Project-based learning	92	89	85	87
Interactive methods	85	91	88	83
Cooperative learning	78	95	81	89
Problem-based learning	88	82	94	79
Digital technologies	91	87	90	86

As can be seen from the table, project-based learning showed the highest result in developing students' independence. Cooperative learning proved to be the most effective method for improving teamwork, while problem-based learning demonstrated the highest effectiveness in developing decision-making skills. Digital technologies produced relatively

balanced results across all indicators. This shows that, in a synergetic educational environment, digital tools are useful for monitoring the management process, distributing tasks, and rapidly evaluating learning outcomes.

The obtained results show that management abilities are not formed through one separate method, but through the integration of several pedagogical factors. Project-based learning develops students' independence, while cooperative learning strengthens collective responsibility and collaboration. Problem-based learning teaches students to make decisions in real-life and complex situations.

In a synergetic educational environment, the teacher does not act only as a transmitter of knowledge. The teacher becomes a mentor, facilitator, and coordinator of the educational process. The student, in turn, becomes an active subject who plans tasks, organizes group activity, evaluates results, and makes decisions.

The results of the study show that project activity, cooperative assignments, problem-based situations, mentoring, and reflective assessment should be applied as a single integrated system in order to develop students' management abilities effectively.

Conclusion

A synergetic educational environment is an effective pedagogical basis for forming students' management abilities. Management ability consists of the integration of such skills as independent planning, priority setting, coordination of teamwork, decision-making, leadership, and reflection.

The study conducted with 84 students demonstrated the practical effectiveness of the synergetic approach. Project-based learning, cooperative learning, and problem-based learning were found to be important in developing different components of management abilities.

As a practical recommendation, it is advisable to introduce a synergetic module aimed at developing management abilities in higher education institutions. This module should combine project tasks, small-group work, problem-solving activities, mentoring, and reflective assessment.

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